

Preparation and Characterization of Hydroxyapatite from Calcium Carbonate of Clam Shell (Biowaste)

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Abstract

In the present work, clam shell is basically made up of calcium carbonate. An attempt is made to convert calcium carbonate of clam shell to hydroxyapatite (HAp) by means of wet precipitation method. All the carbonate phases in the clam shell were decomposed to calcium oxide at 900 °C after 6 hours of heating. The calcined calcium oxide were then treated with nitric acid to form $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. To prepare HAp powder, $(\text{NH}_4)_2 \text{HPO}_4$ and prepared $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in ammoniacal media were kept to Ca/P stoichiometry ratio 1.67 to produce hydroxyapatite (HAp) and it was designated as (HAp-1). The prepared HAp-1 powder was characterized by FT IR, SEM, TG-DTA, EDXRF and XRD. HAp can be used as a substitute material for bone in orthopedic.

Keywords: clam shell, hydroxyapatite, wet precipitation method, calcium carbonate

Introduction

This study attempts to search an alternative material for permanent replacement implants on the human body or without re-surgery. One alternative local materials that has big potential because it has the same composition as the bone is seashells (clam shell). Clam shell has a high level of hydroxyapatite (high calcium), the most important part in the human structural bones. Clam shell has higher calcium composition. Such fine powder can be used as a raw material for bone implants and artificial bone as well (Abraham,1963).

Hydroxyapatite is a major mineral component of human bones. They are chemically similar to the mineral component of bones and hard tissues in mammals. It is the most widely accepted biomaterial for the repair and reconstruction of bone tissue defects. Hydroxyapatite is a naturally occurring mineral form of calcium apatite with the formula $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$. Hydroxyapatite is the hydroxyl end member of the complex apatite group. The OH^- ion can be replaced by fluoride, apatite group (Amit, 2010).

Synthetic HAp is known to be similar to naturally occurring HAp on the basis of crystallographic and chemical studies. Because synthetic HAp is thermodynamically stable at physiological pH and osteoconductive, it has been widely used in hard tissue replacement and reconstruction application such as implant coatings and bone substitutes (Aida, 2009).

The main aim of this research is to study on preparation and characterization of hydroxyapatite from Calcium Carbonate of Clam clam shell (biowaste).

To fulfill of main aim is following objectives:

- To collect the sample from in front of Sittway market
- To prepare clam shell powder sample by mean of grinding method
- To prepare the HAp powder sample by wet precipitation method
- To characterize the HAp (HAp-1) powdered samples by using FT IR, SEM, EDXRF, XRD and TG-DTA techniques

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Materials and Methods

The chemicals used in this present work will from British Drug House Chemical Ltd., Poole, England; Kanto Chemical Co. Inc, Japan. All chemicals were of reagent grade and were used as received. Instruments employed in this present work consist of lab ware, glassware and other supporting facilities.

Scientific Classification

Kingdom	:Animali a
Family	:Veneridae
Phylum	:Mollusc
Class	: Bivalvia
Scientific name	: <i>M.mercenaria</i>
English name	:Clam
Myanmar name	:Gone

Sample Collection and Preparation of hydroxyapatite powder

The clam shell was collected from Sittway market. This collected sample was washed with tap water and rinsed in distilled water to remove the mud sand and other impurities. The clean and dried clam shell were ground in mortar and pestle. The powdered sample was stored in an air-tight container to prevent moisture and other contamination. The dried powdered sample was used to determine mineral and characterize.

Dried powdered sample clam shell was calcined in an electrical muffle furnace (KSL 1100X) at 900 °C so that all organic matter and protein escape out. Clam shell was transformed into calcium oxide by releasing carbon at 900 °C for 6 hours. CaO obtained from clam shell was converted into calcium nitrate [Ca(NO₃)₂] in concentrated nitric acid under constant stirring. To synthesize HAp powder 0.5M (NH₄)₂HPO₄ solution was prepared and added with continuous stirring to a solution of 0.5M Ca(NO₃)₂.4H₂O to keep 1.67 Ca/P ratio and vigorously stirred 30 minutes. At the same time pH was observed and then adjusted 10.5 by adding drop wise 1M ammonium hydroxide [NH₄OH] solution. The suspension was well-stirred (1000 rpm) using magnetic stirred for 2 hour and aged for overnight with ice bath. A white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was subjected vacuum filtrating using buchner funnel, repeatedly washed to obtain pH 7 with deionized water and filtered again. The precipitates were dried at 80 °C for 48 hours. The hydroxyapatite powder (HAp-1) is prepared from clam shell using low temperature by wet precipitation method. (Gergely, 2010)

Results and Discussion

Table 1 is shown the yield percent of CaO, Ca(NO₃)₂ and prepared HAp-1. Clam shell is main source of calcium oxide. So calcium is the richest in the hydroxyapatite.

Table .1 Yield Percent of CaO, Ca(NO₃)₂ and Prepared HAp

Sr. No	Name of product	Yield Percent (%)
1	CaO from Clam Shell	94.96
2	Ca(NO ₃) ₂	76.67
3	HAp 1	70.0

Characterization of Hydroxyapatite Samples

FTIR analysis

Figure 1 and 2 show the FT IR spectra of CaO powder from clam shell and hydroxyapatite from clam shell calcined at 900 °C. The data of absorption bands and possible assignment of these samples are below mention.

Figure 1 FT IR spectrum of CaO powder from clam shell

Figure 2 FT IR spectrum of HAp-1

From FT IR spectrum of CaO powder from clam shell (Figure 1) is shown a wave number of 3641 cm^{-1} . Hydrated CaO exhibited a sharp peak due to the presence of hydroxyl group in $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. This sharp peak could be used to demonstrate the presence and quality the amount of CaO. In the FT IR of calcined at calcined $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the band of C-O stretching from CO_3^{2-} 1479 cm^{-1} and this sharp peak could be used to demonstrate the presence and quantity the amount of CaO.

In the FT IR spectrum of HAp-1, the band of C-O stretching from CO_3^{2-} 1462 cm^{-1} . The band of P-O stretching from PO_4^{3-} was shifted to lower frequencies in 961 cm^{-1} . The band of P-O bending from PO_4^{3-} were 601 cm^{-1} and 569 cm^{-1} . From FT IR analysis prepared HAP contain hydroxyl group, residual carbonate group and phosphate group.

SEM analysis

Figure 3 shows the surface morphology of hydroxyapatite powder From SEM analysis, the calcination temperature $900\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ shows agglomerate.

Figure 3 SEM micrograph of HAp-1 powder

EDXRF analysis

The present of calcium in clam shell are found in organic and inorganic combination. Relative elemental concentrations in clam shell were qualitatively determined by using EDX-700 Spectrometer Shimadzu Co. Ltd., Japan. The principle minerals occurring in the clam shell and hydroxyapatite are calcium, phosphorous, silicon, strontium, ion, potassium, manganese and sulphur. It was observed the most of the calcium element in clam shell and hydroxyapatite. The result shows in Figure 4.

Figure 4 (a) EDXRF spectrum of CaO powder from clam shell and (b) HAP-1 powder XRD analysis

X-ray diffraction analysis was done to the dried powder CaO samples and HAP-1 powder. The strong peaks in the XRD pattern are shown the characteristics of HAP-1 and matched with the JCPDS file No.09-432 of hydroxyapatite by using Debye -Scherer formula. Figure 5 shows XRD diffractogram of HAP-1 powder and Table 5 shows the average crystallite size of HAP powder. Table 2 shows the average crystallite size of HAP powder is 35.64 nm.

Figure 5 XRD diffractogram of HAP powder

Table 2 Crystallite Size of HAp Powder (HAp-1)

No	2 θ	h k l	β (FWHM)	Crystallite size (nm)
1	31.575	(2 2 1)	0.209	39.70
2	32.016	(-2 2 2)	0.229	36.24
3	32.720	(-3 6 0)	0.142	58.44
4	33.821	(-2 4 2)	0.535	15.51
5	53.657	(-1 1 4)	0.293	28.32
Average Crystallite Size (nm)				35.64

TG-DTA analysis

On the basis of TG-DTA profiles, Figure 6 showed that TG-DTA thermogram of HAp-1 powder. From TG-DTA results in Figure 6, there is no weight loss due to the absence of absorbed water or bound water at the temperature range 38-390°C. The sharp endothermic peak 425.75°C is obtained. In which 21.70% loss in weight at ranging temperature from 400-600°C due to the dehydroxylation of interlayer water in HAp sample.

Figure 6 TG-DTA thermogram of HAp powder (HAp-1)

Conclusion

The hydroxyapatite powder (HAp-1) is prepared from clam shell using low temperature by wet precipitation method. The yield percent of CaO from clam shell is 94.96 %. The yield percent of prepared hydroxyapatite (HAp-1) is 70 %. From EDXRF analysis, the principle minerals occurring in the clam shell and hydroxyapatite are calcium, phosphorous, silicon, strontium, ion, potassium, manganese and sulphur. So clam shell is the main source of calcium oxide. From FT IR analysis prepared HAp-1 contain hydroxyl group, residual carbonate group and phosphate group. From XRD analysis, the preparation of HAp-1 has phase pure with the absence of CaO and other secondary phases. The average crystallite size of HAp powder is 35.64 nm. From SEM analysis, the calcinations temperature of 900 °C is agglomerate. From TG-DTA results, the temperature range 400-600 °C, there is an endothermic peak with a little weight loss for HAp-1. The preparation of HAp-1 has thermal stability.

It can be used as a substitute material for bone and teeth in orthopedic dentistry field. It is more effective biomedical applications.

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